

Synthesis of 6-Alkyl/Aralkyl-5a,11-dihydro-9-nitro[1]benzopyrano[2,3-b][1,5]benzodiazepin-13-ones as Possible Antipsychotic Agents

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Manuscript received 27 April 1987, accepted 12 April 1988

The condensation of 3-formylchromones with *N*-alkyl- or aralkyl-4-nitro-*o*-phenylenediamines has been studied under two different experimental conditions. The products have been characterised by their analytical and spectral data.

THOUGH benzo-fused benzodiazepines and their derivatives have been studied extensively in view of their pharmacological importance¹, considerably little work is reported in respect of the benzopyranobenzodiazepinones, more so with the *N*-substituted-benzopyranobenzodiazepinones. It is known that both the benzopyranone and benzodiazepinone systems are biologically more important and an *N*-substituent would potentiate biological activities^{2,3}. So, it was felt worthwhile to undertake the synthesis of the title compounds.

The required four differently substituted 3-formylchromones (4a-d) have been prepared as reported earlier⁴. Two of the five *N*¹-substituted-4-nitro-*o*-phenylenediamines (3) are known and the rest being prepared for the first time. Each of the *o*-phenylenediamine has been condensed with four different 3-formylchromones under two different experimental conditions, viz. in hot glacial acetic acid and in hot benzene in presence of *p*-toluene sulphonic acid.

The products obtained under the former condition, have been characterised as their corresponding Schiff bases, i.e. 3-[*N*-[2-(substituted-amino)-5-nitrophenyl]formimidoyl]chromones (5) by their analytical and spectral data. For instance, the spectral data of the product obtained from the condensation of 6-methyl-3-formylchromone (4; R₂=CH₃) and *N*¹-benzyl-4-nitro-*o*-phenylenediamine (3; R=CH₂Ph) revealed ν_{\max} 3360 (sec. NH), 1630 (C=O), 1610 (C=N) and 1520 cm⁻¹ (Ar-NO₂); δ (CDCl₃) 2.41 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃), 3.58 (2H, d, CH₂Ph), 4.7 (1H, t, NH), 6.8-8.0 (10H, m, Ar-H), 8.1 (1H, dd, *J* 2 and 9 Hz, C₇-H), 9.0 (1H, s, CH=N), 9.2 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz, C₈-H); *m/z* 413. Thus, it could be confirmed that the compound obtained is 3-[*N*-[2-(benzylamino)-5-nitrophenyl]formimidoyl]chromone (5; R=CH₂Ph; R₂=CH₃).

The products obtained under the latter conditions have been similarly characterised as their corresponding 6-alkyl- or aralkyl-5a,11-dihydro-[1]benzopyrano[2,3-*b*][1,5]benzodiazepin-13-ones

(6). Ir spectra of these compounds exhibited characteristic bands at 3340 (NH), 1645 (C=O) and 1510 cm⁻¹ (Ar-NO₂). They showed no absorption characteristic of C=N indicating them to be the dihydrobenzopyranobenzodiazepinones. It is suggested that 5 results as an intermediate which undergoes cyclisation by the nucleophilic 1,4-addition (Michael addition) of the secondary amino group on C₈-carbon of the benzopyranone system yielding the respective 6. This has been found to be contrary to the earlier report⁵.

Experimental

Melting points of the compounds were determined in open capillaries using a Toshniwal melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra

(nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 283 infracord spectrophotometer, pmr spectra on a Varian EM-360 spectrophotometer using TMS as internal standard and mass spectra on a Jeol JMS-D 300 at 70 eV.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, AND PHYSICAL, DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	R	Mol. formula	M.p.** °C	Yield %	Nitrogen % : Found/(Calcd.)		
N-Alkyl/aralkyl-2,4-dinitroanilines (2)							
2a	CH ₃	C ₇ H ₇ N ₂ O ₄	74 ^a	60	—		
2b	C ₆ H ₅	C ₉ H ₉ N ₂ O ₄	80	65	19.89 (19.97)		
2c	(CH ₂) ₂ - N(CH ₂) ₂	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₄	145	60	20.87 (20.97)		
2d	C ₆ H ₁₁	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₄	110	72	15.85 (15.93)		
2e	CH ₂ Ph	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₄	116 ^b	68	—		
N¹-Alkyl/aralkyl-4-nitro-o-phenylenediamines (3)							
3a	CH ₃	C ₇ H ₉ N ₂ O ₂	175 ^c	75	—		
3b	C ₆ H ₅	C ₉ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂	115	62	23.18 (23.25)		
3c	(CH ₂) ₂ - N(CH ₂) ₂	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₂	178	80	23.52 (23.61)		
3d	C ₆ H ₁₁	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂	140	75	17.87 (17.95)		
3e	CH ₂ Ph	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂	180 ^d	75	—		
3-[N-[2-(Substituted-amino)-5-nitrophenyl]formimidoyl]-chromones (5)							
	R ¹	R ²	R				
5A 1	H	H	CH ₃	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₄	190	65	12.95 (13.02)
2	H	H	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₄	195	75	12.42 (12.48)
3	H	H	(CH ₂) ₂ - N(CH ₂) ₂	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ N ₄ O ₄	180	80	14.20 (14.27)
4	H	H	C ₆ H ₁₁	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₄	175	70	10.72 (10.78)
5	H	H	CH ₂ Ph	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₄	85	77	10.52 (10.59)
5B 1	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₄	80	70	12.42 (12.51)
2	H	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₄	200	68	11.96 (12.04)
3	H	CH ₃	(CH ₂) ₂ - N(CH ₂) ₂	C ₂₀ H ₂₃ N ₄ O ₄	210	60	13.72 (13.81)
4	H	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₁₁	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₄	125	72	10.37 (10.45)
5	H	CH ₃	CH ₂ Ph	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₄	192	80	10.16 (10.21)
5C 1	H	Cl	CH ₃	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₄ Cl	165	70	11.74 (11.82)
2	H	Cl	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₄ Cl	184	66	11.25 (11.34)
3	H	Cl	(CH ₂) ₂ - N(CH ₂) ₂	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₄ Cl	210	60	13.06 (13.10)
4	H	Cl	C ₆ H ₁₁	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₄ Cl	115	75	9.86 (9.91)
5	H	Cl	CH ₂ Ph	C ₂₃ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄ Cl	105	72	9.64 (9.73)
5D 1	OH	Cl	OH	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄ Cl	120	72	11.31 (11.36)
2	OH	Cl	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄ Cl	110	67	10.87 (10.94)
3	CH ₃	Cl	(CH ₂) ₂ - N(CH ₂) ₂	C ₂₀ H ₂₃ N ₄ O ₄ Cl	200	72	9.45 (9.53)
4	OH	Cl	C ₆ H ₁₁	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₄ Cl	120	80	9.54 (9.60)
5	OH	Cl	CH ₂ Ph	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄ Cl	130	75	9.36 (9.44)

(Table 1 contd.)

6-Alkyl/aralkyl-5a,11-dihydro-9-nitro[1]benzopyrano[2,3-b][1,5]benzodiazepin-13-ones (6)							
6A 1	H	H	OH ₂	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₄	180	76	13.00 (13.11)
2	H	H	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₄	120	86	12.42 (12.49)
3	H	H	(CH ₂) ₂ -N(CH ₃) ₂	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ N ₄ O ₄	192	60	14.20 (14.26)
4	H	H	C ₆ H ₁₁	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₄	196	70	10.72 (10.81)
5	H	H	CH ₂ Ph	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₄	115	75	10.52 (10.59)
6B 1	H	OH ₂	CH ₂	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₄	100	65	12.44 (12.52)
2	H	OH ₂	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₄	250	60	11.96 (12.03)
3	H	OH ₂	(CH ₂) ₂ -N(CH ₃) ₂	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ N ₄ O ₄	215	55	13.72 (13.78)
4	H	OH ₂	C ₆ H ₁₁	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₄	128	80	10.37 (10.45)
5	H	OH ₂	CH ₂ Ph	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₄	92	75	10.16 (10.25)
6C 1	H	Cl	CH ₂	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₄ Cl	145	62	11.74 (11.82)
2	H	Cl	CH ₂ OH ₂	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄ Cl	187	75	11.95 (11.34)
3	H	Cl	(CH ₂) ₂ -N(OH ₂) ₂	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₄ Cl	218	56	13.06 (13.01)
4	H	Cl	C ₆ H ₁₁	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₄ Cl	120	60	9.82 (9.89)
5	H	Cl	CH ₂ Ph	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₄ Cl	110	57	9.62 (9.70)
6D 1	CH ₃	Cl	CH ₂	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄ Cl	135	50	11.30 (11.39)
2	CH ₃	Cl	CH ₂ CH ₂	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄ Cl	155	76	10.87 (10.95)
3	CH ₃	Cl	(CH ₂) ₂ -N(CH ₃) ₂	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ N ₄ O ₄ Cl	204	70	9.46 (9.56)
4	OH ₂	Cl	C ₆ H ₁₁	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₄ Cl	132	50	9.52 (9.58)
5	OH ₂	Cl	CH ₂ Ph	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₄ Cl	117	75	9.32 (9.41)

*C, H, N analyses were found satisfactory. **M.p.: ^alit. 75°; ^blit. 116°; ^clit. 175°, ^dlit. 180°.

N¹-Alkyl/aralkyl-4-nitro-o-phenylenediamines :

N-Alkyl/aralkyl-2,4-dinitroanilines (2a-e). *General procedure* : To a solution of 2,4-dinitrochlorobenzene (1a-e; 0.02 mol) in methanol (10 ml), an appropriate amine (0.02 mol) and pyridine (5 ml) were added and heated under reflux for 3 h. Methanol was then removed from the reaction mixture under reduced pressure and the residue triturated with ice-cold water. The resulting product was filtered and recrystallisation from a suitable solvent.

*N*¹-Alkyl/aralkyl-4-nitro-o-phenylenediamines (3a-e). *General procedure* : To a suspension of *N*-alkyl/aralkyl-2,4-dinitroaniline (2a-e; 0.02 mol) in water (10 ml) were added ammonium chloride (4.0 g), ammonium carbonate (2.0 g) and ammonia solution (2 ml). Then a solution of sodium sulphide (5.0 g in 15 ml of water) was added slowly in small portions at a time while shaking. The reaction mixture was finally warmed on a water-bath at 60° for 1 h. The resulting berry coloured solid was filtered, washed with small portions of cold water, dried and recrystallised from benzene.

3-[N-[2-(Substituted amino)-5-nitrophenyl]formylmido]chromones (5). *General procedure* :

3-Formylchromone (4a-d; 0.023 mol) and *N*¹-alkyl/aralkyl-4-nitro-o-phenylenediamine (3a-e; 0.023 mol) were dissolved separately in hot glacial acetic acid (20 ml) and mixed together while shaking. The reaction mixture was warmed on a water-bath until a clear dark red solution was obtained. Then, it was poured onto crushed ice with stirring. The resulting product was filtered and washed thoroughly with small portions of cold water and recrystallised from a suitable solvent.

6-Alkyl/aralkyl-5a,11-dihydro-9-nitro[1]benzopyrano[2,3-b][1,5]benzodiazepin-13-ones (6). *General procedure* :

A mixture of 3-formylchromone (4a-d; 0.011 mol), appropriate *N*-alkyl/aralkyl-4-nitro-o-phenylenediamine (3a-e; 0.010 mol) and *p*-toluene sulphonic acid (0.1 g) in dry benzene (100 ml) was heated under reflux using a Dean-Stark water trap for 2 h. Benzene was then removed from the reaction mixture by distillation and the residual oily

liquid was triturated with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) to get the product. It was recrystallised from a suitable solvent.

The physical and analytical data of the compounds is presented in Table 1.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the authorities of Kakatiya University for facilities and encourage-

ment. One of the authors (V.M.R.) is grateful to the U.G.C., New Delhi, for financial assistance.

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